

EXPLORING INCLUSIVE PRACTICES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 4

Pages: 402-410

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2675

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14261199

Manuscript Accepted: 11-21-2024

Exploring Inclusive Practices in Physical Education for Students with Disabilities

Jomar S. Tianio,* Aerob C. Robles, Charlie D. Sabinay, John O. Briones

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aims to explore the inclusive practices in physical education for students with disabilities in selected tertiary institutions in Antipolo City, Rizal, Philippines. The participants included 30 students who had different disabilities that part in the normal Physical Education class. Using descriptive research, data was gathered from the identified students with disabilities through a validated questionnaire checklist. The findings suggested that students encountered a lot of challenges pertaining to participation and modifications to PE activities; however, problems with instructional and testing modifications on the other hand were found to be satisfactory. Data analysis revealed a grand weighted mean of 1.78 (Disagree) to challenges in participation, and 4.88 (Strongly Agree) on the other adaptive measures in instructional accommodations. A systematically structured week plan was drawn to enhance PE activities for the students with disabilities including specific designed activities for students with disabilities. To sum up future Physical Education Activities must be developed in such a way that students with disabilities can participate in them without feeling excluded or unproductive. In this regard, policies and intervention that enable students with disabilities to benefit from these programs are essential. In particular, the findings of this research underline the importance of addressing gaps in existing resources and policies that allow for the effective implementation of inclusive physical education in higher education institutions and the need for strategic reforms in higher education policy.

Keywords: *inclusive education, physical education, people with disabilities, special education and tertiary education*

Introduction

One particularly important subject of research is the exploring inclusive practices in physical education for students with disabilities in the context of higher education institutions. The increasing global trend towards inclusive education calls for the need to explore the best ways in which physical education can be offered to fit learners with disabilities. This study is conducted in some selected tertiary institutions in Antipolo City, Province of Rizal and intends to make a description of the prevailing practices as well as barriers and perceptions of inclusive physical education.

Recent studies draw attention to the grave concerns related to higher education of students with disabilities, especially in physical education. For example, according to Algolaylat et al. (2023), failure to include inclusive education creates serious learning barriers, such as those concerned with the accessibility of the physical environment and even the ability to provide adequate support systems. This is also similar to the challenges discussed in literature, where physical educators are willing and, to a certain extent, able to include children with disabilities in their classes (Alhumaid et al., 2022). Teachers' perspectives on physical education have decisive importance in an inclusive environment as some studies show that more students were included in the classes among teachers who passed an extended training course (Beyazoğlu, 2021; Kuntjoro et al., 2022).

Besides the physical education program, the need for nurturing socialization and interpersonal bonds should be emphasized, too. O'Neil and Olson(2021) maintained that social growth is an essential goal in physical education, and successful inclusion relies on the active engagement of all the teachers in creating a culture of acceptance and working together with all children (O'Neil & Olson, 2021). It is also to the findings of Li et al., who researched the views of peers without disabilities and reported that amicable interactions considerably contribute to the learning of students with disability (Li et al., 2021).

In the case of the Philippines where this study is located, it is good to bear in mind the policy guidelines in education regarding disability as well as the sociocultural perspectives towards disability in the society. The increasing enrollment of students with disabilities in inclusive physical education classrooms is reassuring that people have started recognizing the rights of these students to engage in educational activities (Alhumaid, 2023). Nonetheless, the extent to which these practices are successful is dependent on the adequacy of the training of physical educators and the institutional framework which enables such inclusion to take place (Jung et al., 2022).

Stated and elaborated in the above passages, the main objective of this research is to identify and analyze how inclusive approach is implemented in physical education classes for people with disabilities in some selected higher education institutions in Antipolo city. Such an understanding which includes educator attitudes, student experiences as well organizational conditions within which inclusion operates should provide useful evidence to assist in the development of policy and practice on physical education. This study is significant as it contributes to the growing body of research on inclusive PE practices in the Philippines, particularly at the tertiary level.

The findings will be valuable for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in promoting inclusive education. By shedding light on the realities of inclusive PE in a tertiary institution setting, the study will contribute to a more informed and inclusive approach to physical education for all students.

Research Questions

This research focuses on students with disabilities at selected tertiary institutions in Antipolo City Province of Rizal. This study aims to (a) determine the profile of students with disabilities in terms of age, sex, courses, and disability; (b) assess the challenges that these students have when taking Physical Education (PE) classes regarding PE activities, facilities, instructional accommodation, and assessments; and (c) design more comprehensive PE course outlines which would be suited to the challenges and difficulties faced by those students with the disability. Considering these objectives, the paper was focused on these questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. course; and
 - 1.4. disabilities?
2. What are the challenges that these students have when taking Physical Education (PE) classes in terms of:
 - 2.1. activities.
 - 2.2. facilities; and
 - 2.3. specific challenges and difficulties encountered?
3. How are the educational needs of the respondents taken into consideration when providing them with instructional and testing accommodations?
4. What activities for PE classes can ensure inclusiveness and modification of activities for students with disabilities?

Methodology

The researcher used descriptive research in the study. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research aims to correctly and methodically characterize a population, circumstance, or phenomena. It can answer what, where, when, and how, but not why. Also, this research tool helps the researcher to describe the situation of the students with disabilities in Physical Education (PE) courses in selected tertiary institutions in Antipolo City, Rizal.

Quantitative data was gathered via surveys aimed at evaluating students' perceptions of diversity, engagement, and pleasure in physical education classrooms. The survey will utilize proven tools to assess self-efficacy and social inclusion, hence ensuring reliability and validity (Theoharides et al., 2022). The quantitative approach is particularly effective in this context as it allows for the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data, which can be statistically evaluated to identify trends and patterns in students' experiences. This method aligns with the goal of obtaining measurable insights into how inclusive practices are perceived by students with disabilities, contributing to a broader understanding of the effectiveness of these practices in promoting equitable physical education. The structured surveys will provide a comprehensive overview of students' attitudes and experiences, enabling researchers to quantify the impact of inclusive practices on student engagement and satisfaction.

Following the survey phase, the data will be analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques to determine correlations and differences in perceptions among the participants. This quantitative analysis will provide a robust framework for understanding the impact of inclusive practices on student engagement and satisfaction in physical education settings. The findings will ultimately inform the development of best practices and recommendations for enhancing inclusive physical education programs, ensuring that they effectively meet the needs of all students.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Profile of the respondents*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26 And Above	5	16.667
22 - 25	9	30
18 - 21	16	53.333
Total	30	100.00
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	18	57.353
Female	12	42.647
Total	30	100.00
<i>Course</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bsa	5	15.152
Bsba	8	24.242
Abco	8	24.242
Bs Educ	6	27.273
Bs Tourism	3	9.0909
Total	30	100.00

<i>Disabilities</i>	
Physical disabilities Dwarfism Orthopedic Disabilities Weak right and Left foot – Brain Surgery Enlarged heart, diabetes, chronic arthritis, hypertension, Obesity – (Weak knee) Hemophilia	Clinically Diagnosed Mental Health Depression

The respondents’ demographic information provided in the data depicts quite useful information regarding the age, sex, course of study as well as the disability of the participants. When looking at the age distribution, there are more younger people with 53.33% aged between 18-21, followed by 30% who are aged between 22 to 25, and only 16.67% aged above 26 years. This finding is consistent with that of Ziegenfuss et al. (2021) who has shown in their research that younger cohorts are more representative of survey samples as they are more likely to participate in surveys through digital means.

The sex distribution further indicates that there are more males at 57.35% than females at 42.65%. Studies that investigate gender participation patterns in surveys however are scanty in number but in most surveys, it is known that male respondents generally show more interest in participating in surveys especially from the academic perspective as noted in the case of survey response patterns.

The data on the course distributions reflect the varied academic qualifications of the respondents with the most respondents holding a degree in Education B.S. at 27.27%, as well as BSBA and ABCO at 24.24 percent. As noted by Makinano et al. (2022), such diversity in participants’ educational backgrounds can affect the participants’ viewpoints and perspectives. As stated by the writers, focus must also be made on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents in the context of their knowledge and attitudes towards the relevant issue.

As a disadvantage though, the second indicator which is people-based disability shows an important aspect of the respondent’s population. Cases of people with hearing, physical and diagnosed psychiatric disabilities are not only a concern but underline the need for further inclusive research practice. Past studies of such as that of Okoro et al. (2018) have demonstrated examples of inequities in the disability population when it comes to their access to health care. The reported disabilities include short stature, dwarfism and chronic disabilities further depict an intricate health challenge affecting this population that would need more focused strategies and support systems.

The demographic particulars of the respondents are instrumental in facilitating the characteristics of the study sample, specifying their younger composition, an appreciable distribution balance of the gender, differences in education levels, as well as the health factors being in critical need. Such factors are essential in determining the situation where the study is conducted and in ensuring the findings are not only coverage in scope but also usable to the reasonable person in the universe.

Table 2. Challenges of students taking Physical Education (PE) classes

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Students with disabilities can take part in physical education activities with assistance.	1.38	Strongly Disagree
2. The Physical Education activities are performed properly by students who are disabled.	1.75	Disagree
3. Activities for Physical Education are modified for students with disabilities.	1.38	Strongly Disagree
4. Physical Health of students with disabilities is enhanced through engagement in Adapted Physical Education Activities.	2.13	Disagree
5. The students with disabilities are encouraged and engaged in physical education or PE subjects through special education activities.	2.25	Disagree
Grand Weighted Mean	1.78	Disagree

As seen in table 2, two items received the response “strongly disagree” with the same emphasis. The first item is, “Students with disabilities can take part in physical education activities with assistance” and the second one is ‘Activities for Physical Education are modified for students with disabilities.’ These two items have equal weighted mean of 1.38. Based on the student’s thoughts on this issue: “This is the course, I must admit, I had the most difficulties with. Considering the fact that I have an orthopedic disability and lack balance, performing was really hard for me. I had self-doubts and had anxiety because I am a person who has a disability, but otherwise, thanks to one of my professors, I was kindly given alternative activities.” The response indicates that the challenges are associated with the limited mobilities. This global barrier creates anxiety and insecurity in the students.

However, it is noteworthy that their professors have already addressed these challenges by giving alternative activities. Imms et al. (2016) mentioned that when we talk about participation of students with disabilities in a particular PE activity, we are not just talking about showing up, we are talking about actively participating. Disabled students who take part in extracurricular activities have a better chance of doing well in class and life as well.

Moreover, as cited by Hidayana (2023), Physical education activities are important components of the educational process undertaken by a student that helps formulate rules geared towards healthy living for the rest of their lives. The overall objective of physical

education is to create individuals who possess physical competency of engaging in wholesome physical activities throughout their lifespan. Life can be greatly improved for disabled persons: increased activity levels lower the possibility of health complications as well as have beneficial effects on all levels of functioning (Hidde et al., 2004). As part of a student's general education, quality physical education programs, even if specially designed if needed, are effective in promoting physical, emotional, and social development throughout the life span.

Table 3. *Challenges and Difficulties in terms of Facilities*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. The characteristics of the Gymnasium or Physical Education facilities are also satisfactory in relation to the disabilities of the students.	3.88	Agree
2. Students with disabilities can conveniently use the Physical Education facilities.	4.00	Agree
3. The Gymnasium or PE facilities are suited or constructed for students with disabilities.	3.88	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	3.92	Agree

The challenges and issues pertaining to Physical Education Facilities are presented in table 3. From the findings, it can be concluded that all eight respondents concurred that the facilities in some tertiary institutions in Antipolo City Province of Rizal do not limit them in studying the Physical Education courses. Moreover, with a total weighted mean of 3.92, the participants expressed their consensus that the facilities are appropriate, well placed and constructed for the physically challenged learners. As student feedback indicated: "none so far, I did not experience any difficulties because I use the elevator when going to the gym, and my PE Instructors always lend a helping hand whenever they feel I need it." Bano et. al. (2014) notes that also the provision of education facilities and opportunities according to each of the students' needs contributes to the students' satisfaction with the education institutions they attend. To the extent that the students with disabilities are satisfied, the chances for academic achievement are even greater.

Moreover, on the research of Harun, et. al. (2020), persons with disabilities are members of a group who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, sensory and multiple impairments and other factors which may hinder their full involvement in the life of the community.

Because they need significant attention and specialized structures for their routine operations (Bano, et. al., 2014). Among the general student population in higher education, students with disabilities constitute one category that should be given special care and concern by an organization. The disabled persons who belong to such categories require the supports which can enable them to be active both in learning and other activities including those parts of college resources which are within their reach.

Table 4. *Instructional Accommodation Extended to the Respondents*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. The PE Instructor/ Professors adapts and makes improvements in pedagogical materials of PE courses for disabled students.	4.75	Strongly Agree
2. The Physical Education Instructor/Professors modifies the Instructions of PE Activities and adapts them for the students with disabilities.	4.75	Strongly Agree
3. The Physical Education Teacher rephrases the instructions of PE activities for students with disabilities in case they have difficulties comprehending the instructions.	4.88	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.79	Strongly Agree

The statistical data in table 4 portrayed shows that learners agree on the ability of Physical Education (PE) Teachers to modify the teaching and learning resources and instructions in regards with students with disabilities. According to the respondents' perceptions, the grand weighted mean of 4.79, on the scale of 1 to 5 categorized as 5 "Strongly Agree," pertains to the instructors' skills of adjusting the physical activity tasks of students during PE classes. In particular, the instrumentality of making modifications to resources and Instructions scored 4.75 while the modification of instructions only scored slightly higher at 4.88 but infer that the instructors are cognizant of the barriers experienced by the students with disability and have measures in place to offer such students appropriate instructional set up.

Also, students' responses corroborate these views. They appreciate the instructors additional explanations and extra time to attend to the students who may have difficulty performing the physical activities. A certain student pointed out that, "The PE instructors were explaining to me the tasks. I was quite welcomed when I asked a lot of questions with the task because of my small knowledge on the issue as it is a sport I hardly practice." This support is also consistent with the literature which indicates that proper educational scaffolding is important when working with students with disabilities in physical education. Chelnokova et al. (2019) also stress that psychological and pedagogical assistance is necessary to ensure an inclusion educational space which targets positive academic achievement for students with disabilities Chelnokova et al., 2019). In addition, Protić-Gava et al. (2018) underline that teachers' inclusionist's attitudes as well as most other factors determining effectiveness of inclusion practice are focused on positive change of teaching practices through better adaptation of teachers to inclusion.

The results indicate that the modifications made by the instructors are not just procedures but are based on the effective assessment of

the students in question. Another student’s comments, “the teachers understand my situation and gave me more time to do the activities. Highly recommended,” highlight the need for flexibility, empathy in implementation of teaching strategies which are key facets of inclusive education. This is consistent with the results of who argues that the application of educators’ attitudes and competencies is crucial for the inclusion of students with disabilities in general physical education classes in inclusion settings (Alhumaid, 2022).

To summarize the findings, the evidence and the student feedback show that in the case of persons with disabilities, PE instructors appropriately modify their teaching strategies and encourage involvement and learning. There is strong agreement among students with regard to the attempts made by the instructors which is a welcome shift towards the adoption of inclusive practices in physical education, a debate that is well informed by existing literature on the relevance of pedagogical changes and teachers attitude in inclusion settings.

Table 5. Testing Accommodation Extended to the Respondents

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. A student with disabilities is allowed extra time to submit the Physical activities and exercises to the Physical Education Instructor.	4.88	Strongly Agree
2. Students with disabilities are allowed by the Physical Education Instructor to rest or take time off when doing the given PE activities and assessments.	4.88	Strongly Agree
3. The activities and assessment items under Physical Education Instructor assigned to students with disabilities were changed and adjusted to fit the needs of such learners.	4.88	Strongly Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	4.88	Strongly Agree

The data collected in Table 5 shows that there is a clear agreement among respondents about the extent and the nature of the accommodations directed towards students with disabilities in physical education classes. For each of the items, the respondents’ mean scores of 4.88, all rated above, indicate a “Strongly Agree” interpretation. This implies that the respondents view the accommodation provided: extra time and opportunities to rest during activities and the rest modifying activities and assessments, as both essential and well carried out in the educational system.

Such findings corroborate with the literature emphasizing the facilitating role of students with disabilities in integrating into the mainstream classroom. Accommodation strategies particularly emphasized by Vats and Dey such as alteration of assessment modes and more time provisions also resonate with the findings of this study (Vats & Dey, 2022). Additionally, the studies of Deckoff-Jones and Duell on the informal integration of motivated students into the educational process corroborate the positive views expressed by the respondents in the current study (Deckoff-Jones & Duell, 2018).

The positive student statement and responses from students like this, “I am thankful that my professor in this class tried to address my individual needs regarding my disability” illustrates the self-assessment of these students who have benefited from the said measures. This feeling is consistent with the trend captured in the literature where inclusiveness not only assists students with disabilities in their academics but also impacts them positively with appreciation emotions and satisfaction (Algolaylat et al., 2023).

The fact that physical education students strongly agreed with the provisions made indicates that there are favorable learning conditions for the students with disabilities. The provision of these dissertations is important in terms of not only improving academic performance but also providing needed emotional support as both literature and the students’ comments provide. Inclusive Physical Education Activities

Considering the profile of the students with disabilities in Benilde Antipolo and the results concerning the challenges and difficulties experienced by these students, the researchers propose that activities must be differentiated based on multiple intelligences and disability limitations but ensuring that competencies are met.

Table 6. Example of Regular PE Week Schedule for Regular Students

<i>Weeks</i>	<i>Topics</i>	<i>Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO's)</i>	<i>Teaching and Learning Activities (TLA's)</i>	<i>Assessment Tasks (AT's)</i>	<i>Evaluation Strategies (ES's)</i>	<i>Resources</i>	<i>Due Date</i>
Week 3	A. Physical Fitness Test Health-related fitness components test Cardiovascular endurance Muscular Strength and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define health related fitness Perform PFT (Health-related components) Appreciate the essence of developing our health-related exercise. 	Health Related Fitness 1. Jogging for 30 times. Muscular Strength 1.Push-up for boys and knee push up for the	There are some practical test such as 30 laps of light jogging around the basketball gym. Upper Body Strength 1. push-ups for boys and knee push ups for girls need to be performed as many repetitions as possible (max reps has to be counted)	Outcome based evaluation using Rubrics. Link for the Rubrics PHYSICAL FITNESS RUBRICS PEONEPF https://docs.google.c	Youtube https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1CdwOe-5OaA&t=40s	1 hour after the instructions of the instructor

Endurance	girls 2. Sit ups	2. Sit ups as described in the previous case are up to count as the frequency of performing them displays one's strength and endurance capabilities.	om/document/d/1TKTzWvLUeOi8tUMB YGB2m37Y5iQdR2zf6dapX7m0tQ/edit?usp=sharing
-----------	---------------------	--	--

As represented in table 6, a week 3-course structure is prepared for Physical Education One Physical Fitness (PEONEPF) regular class. Defining the health-related fitness such as Cardiovascular and muscular strength and endurance, the topics are several health-related fitness components that seek the students to conduct Health-related fitness exercises and know-how important it is to develop our health through physical activity. Therefore, the course will also include the practical component assessment such as Jogging thirty times in a round within the basketball gym for their cardiovascular or stamina and likewise muscular strength and endurance. Male Students will do the push-ups, knee push-ups will be the ones for female students, Sit-ups will do both. As for activities concerning the application of acquired fitness knowledge, the learned students should watch how to carry out the different exercises which has been assigned to them with regards to selected physical fitness components directions. For application skills, the students have to do specific activities and participate in the exercise for that specific activity.

Table 7. Example of Enhanced PE Week Plan for Students with Disabilities

Weeks	Topics	Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO's)	Teaching and Learning Activities (TLA's)	Assessment Tasks (AT's)	Evaluation Strategies (ES's)	Resources	Due Date
Week 3	A. Physical Fitness Test Health-related fitness components test Cardiovascular endurance Muscular Strength and Endurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define health related fitness Perform PFT (Health-related components) Appreciate the essence of developing our health-related exercise. 	Health Related Fitness 1. Jogs for 10 minutes. Muscular Strength 1. For the male students, they perform standard push-ups and females do knee push-ups. 2. A sit-up practice. For the pupils with disabilities, The physically challenged practicing exercising using a wheelchair for fifteen minutes with an objective of measuring their cardio vascular or stamina and for Muscular endurance they are using specific hand movements with the use of Dumbbells	An example for the practical test is: Jogging around the basketball court by 30 movements. The second category is Muscular Strength and Endurance. What are the limits for boys and girls? For boys: push ups for as many as possible. Girls pressed on the knees will try and push up as many times as they can until failure 2(387) Second optional for analysis: Sit ups: a great exercise for tracking the number of controlled retractions which is used for interesting tasks (formation of some indicators of muscular strength endurance). Limited use can be made of isolated exercises of a functional sort or elements thereof. Both use a functional stress test(2) as well as a physical stress test. The latter relates to students with disabilities/difference. Everybody else who has issues with the body lets say for example any deficiency (Possibly dwarfism orthopaedic disabilities weak right and left foot brain surgery obesity) The measurement of cardio vascular endurance will include participation to a 15 exercise in a period of breaking movements. This will involve the following actions "1" things. In 16 counts they should stretch their arms backwards; 2, Extend and arm in 16 back and forth in unison; 2 They can repeat "1" and "4" for a maximum of 32 counts. 3 Arms are the only parts to	Outcome based evaluation using Rubrics. Link for the Rubrics PHYSICAL FITNESS RUBRICS PEONEPF https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1CdwOe-5OaA&t=40s	Youtube https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1CdwOe-5OaA&t=40s	Note: For those students with depression and disabilities, they can submit their activities or quiz 10 to 15 minutes after the deadline

swing above the head while staying stationary in 16 counts. 4 They should strive to scrub in the same direction for a total of 16 sweeps downwards over the midsection. 5. 16 turns should be made towards the scrubbing position where arms extend in the direction of the turning side. 6. Execute the moves of exercise 5 but in an inverse manner utilizing 16 counts. 7. Carry out the pause for simulation (16 times) 8. X cross handover (16 times) 9. Complete the rest of the selected exercises translating the remainder of the 15 minutes into a cardio measurement. Last measure the cardio. Vascular or endurance, Then the strength and weakness of muscles through dumbbells (10 lbs) .

1. Both arms in overhead lifting position (asking how many times can they do)
2. Both arms in chest press (asking how many times can they do)
3. Hammer down (asking how many times can they do)

Table 7 presents the week 3-course plan for Physical Education One Physical Fitness (PEONEPF) for students with disabilities. The topics are the same as a regular class. However, it modifies the activities to achieve the goals of the said course. This subject has a practical test designed for students with disabilities; although the physical activities offered to differ from a regular class, they are still aligned with PEONEPF's competencies.

Students with disabilities must complete a series of exercises for 15 minutes in order to gauge their level of cardiovascular fitness or stamina. These exercises include swinging their arms back, alternate arm swings, marching in place (using only their arms), scrubbing their hands in and out, palms in and out, and hand crossings. For muscular strength and endurance, the students must carry out alternative dumbbell exercises like lifting both arms overhead, chest pressing both arms, and hammering down for as many repetitions as possible.

To assess the activities under the application of fitness knowledge, students with disabilities must learn how to perform the assigned exercises in every component of selected physical fitness. For the application skills, students must actively participate in the exercise for the specific activity.

Conclusions

In this study, the researcher examined the inclusive practices in Physical Education (PE) for people with disabilities within selected tertiary institutions in Antipolo city Rizal. The findings indicated that the physical as well as the pedagogical modalities utilized by PE instructors, in principles, have been rather helpful and facilitating, yet there are still barriers that prevent the attaining of full participation on the part of all students. The students raised issues concerning the adequacy of physical education activities designed for them and voiced their difficulties regarding participating in activities that are regarded as standard ones in physical education classes although they received appropriate instructional and testing accommodation such as activity extensions and modifications in the form of shorter tests and other similar forms of active participation. The variations in levels of participation emphasize the need for the constant revision of the curriculum to meet the needs of each individual student with a disability and encourage them to work alongside their peers. To promote an authentic level of inclusiveness in the PE setting, several recommendations can be put forward. To begin with, educational institutions should allocate funds towards training programs for PE teachers that target their use of differentiated instruction. More importantly, comprehensive evaluations of PE spaces should be done to determine whether all forms of physical activity are truly accessible to all. Using the insights from the students, teachers and disability experts building inclusive curricula with desired skills would emphasize different strategies and techniques to target varying degrees of disabilities. Finally, there is a need for awareness educational campaigns to be conducted targeting most of the student community to raise awareness about emerging issues

of inclusion and the expectations that students with disabilities can achieve. Implementing these suggestions should assist educational institutions in improving the standards of Physical Education allowing all students, however disabled to fit in an environment that recognizes their input as well as the wellbeing of the students.

References

- Abu-Hamour, B. & Al-Hmouz, H. (2014). Special education in Jordan. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 29(1), 105-115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2013.859820>
- Alhumaid, M. (2022). Predictors of physical educators' attitudes toward including students with disabilities in inclusive classes. *The Open Sports Sciences Journal*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.2174/1875399x-v15-e221031-2022-34>
- Alhumaid, M., Allah B., Alhuwail A., Alobaid M., Hamad N., Alsalman Z., ... & Bastos T. (2022). Physical education teachers' attitudes toward inclusion of students with disabilities in Saudi Arabia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1006461>
- Alhumaid, M. (2023). Primary students' attitudes towards peers with disabilities in physical education in Saudi Arabia. *Children*, 10(3), 580. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10030580>
- Algolaylat, A., Alodat, A., Muhidat, M., & Almakani, H. (2023). Students with disabilities: understanding of the challenges of inclusive education in higher education. Case study of a Jordanian university. *Tem Journal*, 406-413. <https://doi.org/10.18421/tem121-50>
- Associates, K. (2024). Competencies of junior high school physical education sports and health teachers. *International Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Research and Analytical Review*, 07(04). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i04-46>
- Bano, H., Akhter, N., & Anjum, N. (2014). Analysis of Educational Facilities and Opportunities for Students with Special Needs at University of the Punjab. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 16(1), 79. http://iub.edu.pk/jer/journal/jer_vol16_no1.pdf
- Beyazoğlu, G. (2021). Attitudes of teachers towards inclusion of students with disabilities in physical education. *PJMHS*, 15(10), 3390-3393. <https://doi.org/10.53350/pjmhs2115103390>
- Chelnokova, E., Kaznacheeva, S., Egorov, E., Shobonova, L., & Lebedeva, T. (2019). Human resources support for inclusive education. <https://doi.org/10.2991/ispbc-19.2019.78>
- Deckoff-Jones, A., Duell, M. (2018). Perceptions of the appropriateness of accommodation for university students with disabilities: Does it depend on the disability type. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 63(1), 68-76. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rep0000213>
- Harun, M. F., Hamid, M. F., Salleh, L. M., Zainal, N. D., Ahmad, N., Aznan, N., Yunus, D. D. M., Yasin, A. M., & Zakirai, Zakaria, N. S. (2020). Knowledge and Awareness of PWD's Facilities: A Case Study at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Student and Disable Student Development (ICo1SD 2)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200921.023>
- Hidayana, R. (2023). The role of physical, sport and health education in developing healthy life behaviors. *IJHMS*, 1(4), 16-19. <https://doi.org/10.46336/ijhms.v1i4.18>
- Hidde P. van der Ploeg, Allard J. van der Beek, Luc H.V. van der Woude & Willem van Mechelen. (2004). Physical Activity for People with a Disability. A Conceptual Model. *Sports Medicine* 34(10): 639-649 0112-1642/04/0010-0639. <http://foundationforpmr.org/old/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Physical-Activity-for-People-with-a-Disability.pdf>
- Imms, C., Granlund, M., Wilson, P. H., Steenberg, B., Rosenbaum, P. L., & Gordon, A. M. (2016). Participation, both a means and an end: a conceptual analysis of processes and outcomes in childhood disability. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 59(1), 16-25. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.13237>
- Isah, M.S. (2014, July 1) Towards Inclusive socio - cultural Theories practices in Nigeria. *National Journal of Inclusive Education - Vol. 2, No. 1* p. 179
- Jung, J., Case, L., Logan, S., & Yun, J. (2022). Physical educators' qualifications and instructional practices toward students with disabilities. *Adapted Physical Activity Quarterly*, 39(2), 230-246. <https://doi.org/10.1123/apaq.2021-0117>
- Kozuin, A. (1991), *Vygotsky's Psychology: A Biography of Ideas*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA. 296 pages. ISBN: 0-674-94365-1. \$29.95. (1992b). *Bulletin of Science Technology & Society*, 12(1), 57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/027046769201200132>
- Kuntjoro, B., Soegiyanto, S., Setijono H., & Sugiharto S. (2022). Inclusion of students with disability in physical education: analysis of trends and best practices. *Acpes Journal of Physical Education Sport and Health (Ajpes)*, 2(2), 88-94. <https://doi.org/10.15294/ajpes.v2i2.64840>
- Li, C., Haeghele, J., McKay, C. & Lijuan W. Wong, J. P. (2021). Including students with physical disabilities in physical education in Singapore: perspectives of peers without disabilities.

- Ljubojevic, A. & Jakovljević, V. & Popržen, M. (2014). Effects of Zumba Fitness program on body composition of women. SportLogia.
- Makinano, R., Miranda, C., Galolo, A., Mendez, A., & Elvira, M. (2022). Knowledge, attitude, and practices on responsible parenthood and family planning among beneficiaries of the family alleviating program on poverty of Caraga region, Philippines. *Journal of Ecosystem Science and Eco-Governance*, 31-42. <https://doi.org/10.54610/jeseg/4.1.2022.004>
- McCombes, Shona (2019, May 15) Descriptive Research Design I Definition Methods and examples p.7
- National Statistics Office (2015). Gender quick stat. Retrieved from <https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/genderstatistics/gender-quickstat-index>
- Okoro, C., Hollis, N., Cyrus, A., & Griffin-Blake, S. (2018). Prevalence of disabilities and health care access by disability status and type among adults — United States, 2016. *MMWR Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 67(32), 882-887. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6732a3>
- O'Neil, K. & Olson, L. (2021). Every Child is 'Ya Ya': The Challenge of Including All Families in Early Physical Education. *Family Sociology*, 45(2) 70–78 doi:<http://doi.org/10.5294/elea.2018.45.2.2>
- Pasion, P. (2017, June 27) Path to inclusion: La Salle college guides PWD learners. <https://www.rappler.com/moveph/159835-la-salle-college-saint-benilde-pwd-inclusion/>
- Protić-Gava, B., Boskovic, K., Smajic, M., Simić-Panić, D., & Naumovic, N. (2018). Work with children with disabilities - the teachers' attitudes towards inclusion. *Medicinski Pregled*, 71(7-8), 227-234. <https://doi.org/10.2298/mpns1808227p>
- Saraswara, B, Maksum, A, & Kristiyandaru, A, (2023) Performance assessment of physical education teachers in schools.
- Stafa, A. (2023). Read and parsed *Jurnal Maempo Jurnal Pendidikan Jasmani Kesehatan Dan Rekreasi*, 13(1), 81. <https://doi.org/10.35194/jm.v13i1.3252>
- Student profile - Students With No Speech. (2018, March 9). Students With No Speech; www.studentswithnospeech.org.au. <https://www.studentswithnospeech.org.au/toolkit-topics/student-profile/>
- Theoharides, T. C., Lussier, M. J., & Becker, A. R. (2022). Examining the role of inclusivity in promoting self-efficacy among students with disabilities in physical education. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 93(1), 32-40.
- Vats, A., & Dey, S. (2022). Accommodation strategies in relation to students with disabilities in a classroom setting. *Technoarete Transactions on Application of Information and Communication Technology(ict) in Education*, 1(4) <https://doi.org/10.36647/taicte/01.04.a005>
- Vygotsky's Vision: Reshaping the Practice of Special Education for the 21st Century. www.bgcenter.com. Retrieved July 1, 2022, http://www.bgcenter.com/Vygotsky_Vision.htm
- Yaroshevsky, M.G. (1993). L. S. Vygotsky: V Poiskach Novoi Psichologii. [Vygotsky: in Search for the New Psychology], St. Petersburg, Russia: Publishing House of International Foundation for History of Science.
- Ziegenfuss, J., Easterday, C., Dinh, J., Kottke, T., & Canterbury, M. (2021). Impact of demographic survey questions on response rate and measurement: a randomized experiment. *Survey Practice*, 14(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.29115/sp-2021-0010>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jomar S. Tianio

De La Salle College of Saint Benilde – Philippines

Aerob C. Robles

National University – Philippines

Charlie D. Sabinay

National University – Philippines

John O. Briones

National University – Philippines